

ANCIENT GLACIATION IN THE AREA OF UKRAINIAN ANTARCTIC STATION: ICE SHELF OR ICE SHEET?

O.V. Mytrokhyn^{1,2}, V.G. Bakmutov³

¹ Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv, Ukraine; mitrokhin.a.v@ukr.net;

² Institute of Geological Sciences, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine;

³ S. I. Subbotin Institute of Geophysics, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

It is believed that the Bellingshausen Sea in the area of Ukrainian Antarctic Station was once covered by an ice shelf. Fleming in 1940 first proposed this idea based on his study of *fringing glaciers* and *island ice-caps* during British Graham Land Expedition. It was later a priory supported by a number of researchers. Only L. Govorukha drew attention to the glacial exaration and erratics on the Argentine Islands. The reliability of the ice shelf hypothesis, as well as the area, thickness, and motion of the ancient glaciation, has not been discussed by anyone until now.

In 2020, the authors performed the first systematic study of geological evidence of ancient glaciation in the area of the Ukrainian Antarctic Station. Field geological observations covered most of the Wilhelm Archipelago (Booth Island, Hovgaard Island, Petermann Island, Dannebrog Islands, Roca Islands, and Argentine Islands) as well as the separately located Yalour Islands and Berthelot Islands. The main attention was paid to erratic debris, ancient moraines, glacial striation, and glacial landforms.

The field observations confirmed the past presence of the ancient glaciation on the Wilhelm Archipelago and neighbouring islands. The geological age of the glaciation needs clarification. It can be tentatively attributed to the last glacial maximum. At the same time, it was found out that generally accepted ideas about the existence of ancient ice shelf on this territory are erroneous. All available data show that during the last glacial maximum, the Wilhelm Archipelago as well as it surrounding area was a dry land covered by an ancient ice sheet (AIS). A true floating ice shelf could only exist over the narrow area on the Penola Strait, Lemaire Channel, and French Passage.

No deposits that would have formed during the melting of floating ice shelf were found on any of the islands studied. Instead, ancient moraines and erratic debris were discovered. In particular, erratics of alkali feldspar granites, slate and phyllites were transported by AIS to varying distances from their original outcrops to the current location. Erratics were found on all the studied islands, including those furthest towards the open sea. Their distribution outlines the minimum area of the AIS. The specified AIS extended westward from the current coastline of the Kyiv Peninsula for a distance of more than 20 km, reaching the level of the modern isobath -200 m below sea level. The thickness of the AIS can be estimated from the highest elevations at which erratics were found. It should exceed 120 m.

Glacial striation as well as glacial landforms, namely *the ram forehead* and *the curly rocks* were formed on bedrocks as a result of glacial exaration. Note that a floating ice shelf does not cause ice exaration. Similar to erratics, glacial landforms and striation also provide information on the area and thickness of the AIS. In addition, they can be used to determine the direction of glacier movement. Numerical observations have revealed that the AIS moved in the direction from the southeast to the northwest. It is significant that the largest bays on the mainland of the Kyiv Peninsula, as well as a long channel between the largest among Argentine Islands, are oriented in this direction.